

THE HARZBURG MANAGEMENT MODEL- A CATALYST FOR INTRAPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract

Purpose – Aims to present a model which creates an environment that offers the employee the freedom to act and think independently, especially through the delegation of responsibility, thus creating the framework for intrapreneurship.

Methodology/approach – A historical review from two main perspectives, the corporate intrapreneurship literature and the elements of a management model, not studied before, but which will bring substantial contribution to intrapreneurship, if implemented.

Findings – There are positive relationships between the Harzburg Management Model (and its dimensions i.e. organizational and structural) and intrapreneurship.

Research limitations/implications – A survey is currently ongoing in order to establish the relationship between the particularities of the model as a factor for increasing motivation and intrapreneurship.

Practical implications – The hereby presented management model could offer a business model which fosters intrapreneurship.

Originality/value – The model offers through its main elements and methods the creation of an intrapreneurial employee which will bring only benefits in the further development of the organization.

Key words: Intrapreneurship, performance, delegation of responsibility.

Introduction

Successful companies figure out that the most important elements in the organization are the ability to use the creativity of managers and employees through the recognition of their behaviours. One of the most important strategies for developing intrapreneurship in organizations is to improve and enhance the intrapreneurial behaviour of employees. The need for innovation in organizations is a topic that is much debated at the moment because intrapreneurship has finally caught the world's attention. Within the specialty literature, we found no relevant research that explicitly investigates the process of how the behaviour of the individual leads to intrapreneurial outcomes on an individual level and subsequently on an organizational level, even though the relationship between the intrapreneur and the organization is what makes an intrapreneur an intrapreneur. Thereof, we propose the Harzburg Management Model, which, with its principle of creating independently thinking and acting employees can lead to a behavioural pattern which will in turn increase intrapreneurial outcomes.

Understanding the term intrapreneurship

One of the most important strategies for developing intrapreneurship in organizations is to improve and enhance the intrapreneurial behavior of employees. Drucker (1985) revealed that the essence of entrepreneurship is innovation. So it is natural for companies to carry out their activities leading to a process of creation. Intrapreneurship is a term introduced by Burgelman (1983) and made prominent by Gifford Pinchot (1985), where Pinchot put forward the terms "intra" and "preneurship" (taken from the word entrepreneur). Pinchot suggests and provides guidance for individuals to be able to give birth and

develop ideas to be transformed into business ventures considering that intrapreneurs are "people who focus on innovation and creativity and who turn dreams or ideas into profitable businesses, operating in an organizational environment. Research on organizational-level intrapreneurship, referred to the term as corporate entrepreneurship (Blanka, 2018), and implies an organization's corporate venturing and strategic renewal activities as a result of its employees' intrapreneurial behaviors and effective use of human resources management. Organizations have successfully implemented the intrapreneurship concept, by allocating their employees' time to work on creating innovative ideas, products and services. In accordance with the basic concept of intrapreneurship, organizations must create an entrepreneurial climate within the company by encouraging the innovation process to employees. Employees are conditioned to improve conventional ways of thinking by motivating them to be able to create new ideas for companies by utilizing company resources or creating truly new products. Thus, this lies in accordance with Drucker's statement (1985) that the essence of entrepreneurship is innovation. The concept of corporate entrepreneurship or intrapreneurship in a company can increase company income and be able to make the company survive in difficult economic conditions. Over the years, the role of employees in organizations has changed. Decision-making processes have become more decentralized and employees are gaining more discretion and responsibility (Foss et al. 2015). This trend goes hand in hand with employees being relied upon to be flexible, proactive and innovative (Giunipero et al. 2005). Rather than being passive recipients of changing jobs and products, employees need to adopt roles as "innovators" and "differentiators" (Bowen 2016). For example, Heinze and Weber (2016) found that intrapreneurial employees implement new logics in organizations by using opportunistic tactics, and leverage small changes to spark larger changes in the broader organization. In addition, Alt and Craig (2016) show that lower-level employees can induce bottom-up socially inspired innovations in for-profit organizations.

Figure 1. Effects of intrapreneurship (author's source)

The Harzburg Management Model as a catalyst for intrapreneurship

Within the specialty literature, we found no relevant research that explicitly investigates the process of how the behavior of the individual leads to intrapreneurial outcomes on an individual level and subsequently on an organizational level, even though the relationship between the intrapreneur and the organization is what makes an intrapreneur an intrapreneur. In this regard, we consider that the main principle of the Harzburg Model, that of having independently thinking and acting employees leads to a behavioral pattern which will increase intrapreneurial outcomes.

For the employee of a company, intrapreneurship means acting independently, thinking like an entrepreneur and pursuing the goals you set yourself in a wide range. Prerequisites for this are creativity,

a wealth of ideas, cost awareness, the ability to cope with setbacks, a minimum of entrepreneurial talent and, last but not least, and teamwork. As a rule, intrapreneurs are the employees which are satisfied with their job. Responsible action, the possibility of contributing your own ideas and thus making a contribution to the success of the company promote motivation and the willingness to get involved within the organization. However, there is also a risk of being overwhelmed. If we consider one of the important features of the Harzburg Model, that of the attribution of total competencies to the employee in his area of activity, giving him the possibility of unlimited initiative and maneuver within the limit of the position, and thus enhancing trust, stability, pride and attachment to the organization, we conclude that this particularity of the model creates an intrapreneurial employee. The essence of the characteristics mentioned, is the motivation that the certain employee now has, within the presented organizational concept, obtaining maximal results, offering a free path towards creation and representing the general impulse towards the superior structures, by alerting them regarding the problems that will most probably occur, before they actually happen. In such a way, the trust and motivation is transmitted to all the staff members. More so, as we will further detail, the management model aims to nurture an environment which offers the employee the freedom to act and think independently, especially through the delegation of responsibility, thus the framework for intrapreneurship is set. The risk of feeling overwhelmed is also decreased if not annulled, within the Harzburg Model, due to the fact that employees have clear delegated tasks within their area of competences, so an overburden is can rarely happen. More so, exactly this clear delegation of tasks and competencies allows the employee the required time for innovation. When he has to make decisions independently, than he must also use innovation in order to surpass different problems. For a company, intrapreneurship means creating framework conditions for a start-up culture in the company and setting an example for this new corporate culture in which the intrapreneurs can develop. At the organizational level of the company, this requires not only the provision of the necessary resources, the creation of success-based incentives, shortening information channels and, above all, that the company transfers project responsibility to the intrapreneur, promotes its work, but also demands results.

Management should give the intrapreneur freedom beyond his or her actual job responsibility and description, but make sure that the freedom is not misused. Suggestions and ideas for innovations are carefully examined and assessed by the management. If an initiative is rejected, the rejection should be reasonably and comprehensibly justified.

Figure 2. Features of intrapreneurial employee promoted by HMM (author's source)

The intrapreneur and an entrepreneur have a lot in common. Both are able to act independently, think like an entrepreneur and have an eye on the costs. You can motivate yourself and engage for a goal. Intrapreneurs and entrepreneurs are ambitious, they are determined, work solution-oriented and are willing to take risks. They see failure as an opportunity and can learn from mistakes.

The difference between intrapreneur and entrepreneur lies in the responsibility and the consequences that their actions can bring. The responsibility of intrapreneurs is usually very limited, thus the responsibility to act and decide within the boundaries of the working area and the thereof assign competencies (an already mentioned particularity of the Harzburg Model). Since intrapreneurship is

usually only a small part of the overall organization of a company, failures usually have no significant influence on the development of the company. If the failures persist, the intrapreneurship ends and the intrapreneur works like a normal employee again. In the worst case, the employer cancels his employment. The responsibility of the entrepreneur is much more far-reaching, and corresponding serious consequences can result in wrong decisions by the entrepreneur. The entrepreneur is responsible for the entire company. Inside and outside. This means that an entrepreneur's decision to do something or not do something has a direct impact on the success of the company, its employees, customers and business partners. The consequences of a series of wrong decisions are usually not limited to a small sub-area. Persistent mismanagement, whether consciously or subconsciously, often leads to the end of the entrepreneurial activity and the economic end of the company. In this regard, we consider the managerial responsibility awarded by the Harzburg Model to the manager/ superior. The superior is the one who bears this responsibility, must make decisions (but after consultation with employee and resting on his know-how and professional input) which influence the whole organization and often also the delegation area of the employee.

We consider that intrapreneurship and the Harzburg management model are not merely a behavior pattern of an individual or an organization, but is about a set of activities of an individual or an organization to get from point A to point B in time, with an increased competitiveness and performance of the organization as the end goal.

The success of the intrapreneur also depends on the organizational context. The organization can facilitate or inhibit the actions of the intrapreneur.

In our systematic literature review, we found that the majority of articles focused on organizational factors influencing intrapreneurship. This systematic literature review revealed which organizational factors facilitate the employee to act as such. Thus, we want to explore the relationships among the factors identified and the HMM. First, the most important factors found in the specialty literature for enhancing intrapreneurship refer to:

- Receiving management support: the willingness of management to facilitate and promote intrapreneurship including encouraging employees and recognizing that their activities involve some risk-taking and creating a norm within the organization.
- The organizational structure: flexibility of the organization, the flow of information throughout the organization and the centralization of the decision-making process. Open channels of communication and providing mechanisms that allow for ideas to be evaluated, selected and implemented are positively related to intrapreneurship.
- Giving employees autonomy: Giving the employee the freedom to design his/her work and to decentralize the decision-making process results in more intrapreneurial activities and also increases the self-efficacy of employees.
- Rewards and reinforcement: Rewards should be in line with goals and should be based on results.
- Providing the right resources: resources involve time and financial resources. The quality of time is more important than the actual amount of time.

Figure 3. Organizational factors with intrapreneurial outcome (author's source)

Considering this aspect, we find that the organizational factors leading to intrapreneurship correspond to the organizational pattern promoted by the Harzburg Model. So, second, the fact that the factors that have been proven to promote intrapreneurship correspond to the elements of the mentioned management model, we can prove the initial hypothesis, that one of the main performances of this particular model is that of promoting intrapreneurship:

- Management support: Top-management implements general management guidelines which aim to foster recognition and encouragement of the employees through different managerial instruments, such as the appraisal interview or performance review.
- Organizational structure: information flow is performed in more than one direction and under the centralization of the decision-making process, we see the concentration of the decision-process of all the different levels of the hierarchy according to area of activity and competencies.
- Rewards: Motivating employees is a focal point within the HMM. Remuneration is performed according to task fulfillment
- Autonomy: Employee has the freedom to act and decide independently within his area of activity.
- Resources: the resource of time in the sense of quality is offered by using different methods of unloading the employee, or no make him feel overwhelmed by tasks and responsibilities. This creates, as mentioned before, the frame for an innovative behavior but it also offers the job holder the required time frame to performed quality works.

Figure 4. Organizational factors of HMM with intrapreneurial outcome. (author's source)

Discussion and conclusions

We conclude that the Harzburg Management model sets the framework for achieving intrapreneurial employees and this will in turn lead to an increase in organizational performance. It is expected that companies that apply the concept can survive in various business obstacles such as the emergence of foreign competition, technological change, accompanied by a decrease in the number of workers and the quality of labor and other problems. This review confirms the strategic importance of intrapreneurship. It shows the multilevel nature of intrapreneurship by emphasizing the link between individual intrapreneurial behavior and organizational outcomes, thus implying that employees do have a direct impact on the organization's strategic direction. By implementing the Harzburg Management Model in organizations by default, the scenery for intrapreneurship is set. The model offers through its main elements and methods the creation of an intrapreneurial employee which will bring only benefits in the further development of the organization.

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